

RESEARCH ARTICLE | APRIL 19 2023

Recent advances in silicon-based nanostructures for thermoelectric applications

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APL Mater. 11, 040702 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0134208>

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Cite as: APL Mater. 11, 040702 (2023); doi: 10.1063/5.0134208

Submitted: 9 November 2022 • Accepted: 3 April 2023 •

Published Online: 19 April 2023

View Online

Export Citation

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ABSTRACT

In this work, implementations of silicon-based thermoelectric nanomaterials are reviewed. Approaches ranging from nanostructured bulk—i.e., macroscopic materials presenting nanoscale features—to more complex low-dimensional materials are covered. These implementations take advantage of different phonon scattering mechanisms and eventual modifications of the electronic band-structure for the enhancement of the thermoelectric figure of merit. This work is focused on the recent advances in silicon and silicon-based thermoelectric nanomaterials of the last decade—at both the theoretical and experimental level—with the spotlight on the most recent works. Different nanostructures and their fabrication methods are detailed, while the thermoelectric performances and the feasibility of their integration into functional micro-harvester generators are compared and discussed. This Research Update first covers the advances in nanostructured bulk, such as nanometric-sized polycrystals or defect-induced materials. Subsequently, it reviews low-dimensional materials, namely, thin films and nanowires. Later, other complex structures based on nanoporosity, superlattices, or core-shell schemes are detailed. Finally, it is devoted to present examples of the successful implementation of nanostructured silicon into functional thermoelectric devices.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Thermoelectricity is a physical property based on the reversible conversion between heat and electricity. Taking advantage of this intrinsic property, robust and silent solid-state power generation devices can be crafted. Since Thermoelectric Generators (TEGs) do not present moving parts, they feature long lifespans and competitive performance compared to thermal engines at low scales (below ~10 W applications).¹ Thermoelectric (TE) materials with optimal intrinsic properties show a high zT parameter, a dimensionless figure of merit described as

$$zT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa} T,$$

where σ , κ , S , and T are the electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity, Seebeck coefficient, and absolute temperature, respectively.² Currently, best performing bulk thermoelectric materials in the low

temperature range (<400 K) are based on metal chalcogenide alloys with small bandgaps suited for TE generation.³ In the middle and high temperature range (>400 K), half-Heusler, clathrate, and skutterudite compounds have recently shown their potential to achieve beyond the unit zT performances.^{4,5} However, most of these alloys contain elements that are expensive owed to their scarcity and the highly complex geopolitics of the existing reserves. Hence, the economy of some of the key required elements (S, Se, Te, Bi, Pb, Sb, Co, La, Hf, etc.) is delicate, and thus, there is a high and real risk of supply if applied to mass scale applications. Additionally, some of these cited elements are known to be toxic or carcinogenic up to some degree, hindering their use in wearable or health technologies.⁶

Alternatively, for the latter scenarios, flexible and economic polymeric TE materials have been proposed, yet their implementation with the required electronics in functional devices is still in a developing phase.⁷ Hence, during the last decade, large efforts

have been dedicated to the search of thermoelectrically competitive materials based on abundant and biologically and electronically compatible materials. In this regard, silicon, silicon alloys, such as silicon-germanium (SiGe), and other silicides share the attractiveness of being based on the mainstream material used in integrated electronics. Bulk silicon has a relatively high power factor ($PF = \sigma S^2$) at high doping levels. However, with a diamond structure, pure silicon heat conduction is mainly driven by phonons, showing a very high κ of ~ 150 W/m K at room temperature. Precisely, this efficient heat conduction withdrew attention from silicon for many decades as this κ yielded zT values as low as ≈ 0.01 .

Despite this, pioneering works by Hicks and Dresselhaus^{8,9} relaunched the research on these compounds by theoretically predicting how the material properties could be engineered through nanostructuration. In their works, Hicks and Dresselhaus stated how in low-dimensional materials the size of at least one of the constrained dimensions becomes related to the material properties. This happens because the surface-to-volume ratio becomes so large that a significant fraction of all material atoms experiences quantum mechanical effects related to the presence of asymmetries in the surroundings of material boundaries. Nano-dots, nanowires (NWs), and thin films show three, two, and one dimensions constrained to this size. This circumstance results in a modification of both the charge carrier and heat carrier's density of states (DOS), as depicted in Fig. 1(a). Ultimately, this modification alters the population distribution of these carriers and, thus, the thermoelectric properties that depend on it. For the case of charge carriers, the modification of the bandgap-width leads to strong variations in the Fermi energy level E_F , which directly modify the Seebeck coefficient of the material as described by its derived expression from the Boltzmann transport equation with relaxation time approximation,

$$S = \frac{1}{e \cdot T} \left(\frac{\langle \tau \cdot E \rangle}{\langle \tau \rangle} - E_F \right),$$

where e is the electron charge, T is the temperature, $\langle \tau \rangle$ is the average electron scattering rate, and $\langle \tau \cdot E \rangle$ is the product of this scattering rate with the average electron energy. As illustrated in Figs. 1(c) and 1(d), such a shift of the Fermi energy level due to nanostructuration is directly impacting on the $(\langle \tau \cdot E \rangle / \langle \tau \rangle - E_F)$ term.

However, the most relevant consequence of nanostructuration is the enhancement of phonon suppression.¹¹ Several structures such as those illustrated in the right column of Fig. 2 have been engineered by researchers with the aim of tailoring the thermal conductivity by promoting phonon scattering. The left column of Fig. 2 shows all the scattering mechanism that can be addressed in nanostructured materials. Each contribution to the total phonon scattering rate can be added using Matthiessen's rule,

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{tot}} = \sum \frac{1}{\tau_i}.$$

In a defect-free bulk single crystal, main phonon scattering mechanisms are phonon-phonon and phonon-electron events. Such inelastic scatter rates have a square dependence with the phonon frequency ω (see Fig. 3).¹⁹ The addition of impurities—even in small fractions ($> 10^{19}$ cm⁻³)—triggers the scattering of phonons by this mechanism. This is proportional to the number of foreign atoms in the lattice. Since this contribution is proportional to ω^4 (Fig. 3), this mechanism effectively suppresses high frequency phonons.²⁰ Alternatively, the replacement of silicon atoms by some other elements provides another way of increasing phonon scattering.

Special remark can be done in low-dimensional structures, such as nanograins, thin films, or nanowires. There, as the boundary scattering mechanism becomes the dominant process, the phonon spectrum is modulated.²² This strong effect typically takes place when one or more crystal spatial dimensions fall into the submicrometric scale and is typically dependent on the inverse of the constrained system dimension d as the mechanism affects all the phonon frequency spectrum equally (recall Fig. 3).¹² Additionally, depending on the surface of the interfaces, phonon reflections can range from fully specular to fully diffusive in the case of rough structures, being the latter case the most efficient phonon scattering mechanism.^{23,24} Then, in the presence of extremely high Surface-to-Volume Ratios (SVRs), such as the case of highly rough surfaces of nanostructures or nanoporous material, phonons are effectively scattered with a strong ω^B dependency (with B varying from 4 to 0 depending on the pore sizes) and a linear dependency on the SVR.¹³ This mechanism, usually taking place alongside with the reduced size one, is also highly effective for high frequency phonon suppression.

Since phonons can travel a certain distance (mean free path λ) before undergoing scattering, the presence of a material patterning with the same lower characteristic distances can show non-Fourier phonon propagation phenomena.²⁵ Clear examples are patterned films (Fig. 2), where the geometry of the perforated membrane (either aligned or staggered) can modify the thermal conductivity by altering the phonon pathway, which is mainly driven by a ballistic transport in such cases.²⁶ Indeed, Minnich *et al.* developed a

FIG. 1. (a) DOS functions of a bulk semiconductor (continuous line), a nanowire semiconductor of $\phi \sim 50$ nm (dotted line), and a nanowire of $\phi \sim 1$ nm (dashed line). (b) Energy filling for a bulk semiconductor. (c) and (d) Energy filling for a semiconductor nanoconductor of $\phi \sim 50$ nm (c) and $\phi \sim 1$ nm (d). In (b)–(d), values of Fermi level ϵ_F and average energy ϵ are indicated. Shaded areas indicate levels occupied by electrons. Adapted from the work of Gadea *et al.*¹⁰

FIG. 2. Schematics of the different phonon scattering mechanism and a summary of the main nanomaterial approaches that can be implemented. The links relate the scattering mechanism that the nanostructure is engineered for. Phonon scattering representative relationships were extracted from several sources.¹²⁻¹⁸

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spectroscopy technique based on the observation of the ballistic thermal resistance of materials as a function of the heated area.²⁷ With this technique, the phonon mean free path can be measured for any kind of material and shape.

Finally, the presence of superlatticed interfaces can also tune the thermal conductivity. In this case, because the process involves a series of boundary transmissivities, there is no analytical description for a formal scattering rate, but an equivalent τ would be proportional to the inverse of the period ℓ , as the larger number of interfaces increases the reflection of phonons.^{28,29} This modeling can be applied when there is no constructive interference with reflective phonon waves. However, the presence of periodic interfaces produces multiple reflected phonons, created at each interface.

When these phonons frequencies are in phase, they interfere constructively, hindering the propagation of the original wave within the structure. This phenomenon affects specific frequency ranges and is known as the bandgap principle.³⁰ Nevertheless, the aforementioned mechanism describes only diffusive phenomena. For superlattices with interface periodicities below the coherent length—typically slightly smaller than the mean free path λ —a coherent transport can become the dominant mechanism.^{18,31} In such a situation, phonons are no longer scattered at the interfaces, and indeed, decreasing the period further adds more allowed vibrational coherent modes.³² This yields an increase in the thermal conductivity, so a hypothetical scattering rate would be in such a case directly proportional to the period ℓ .

FIG. 3. Possible spectral scattering rate contributions in silicon (top) compared to the spectral Density Of States (DOS). Scattering rates are calculated using the models proposed by Wang and Mingo, Lee *et al.*, Ohishi *et al.*, and Yang *et al.*,^{12,13,16,20} assuming a characteristic length of 100 nm, a heavily boron doping ($5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), and a surface-to-volume ratio of 0.005 nm^{-1} . Spectral DOS obtained from the data of pure silicon available at the Materials Project (ref. mp-149).²¹

Interestingly, advances in *ab initio*—i.e., first principle—calculations in the last decade have allowed researchers to accurately reproduce the phonon transport phenomena described before.^{33,34} Moreover, new codes are arising with the possibility to fully couple electron and phonon transport.³⁵ This has enabled the possibility of forecasting thermoelectric properties on nanomaterials without requiring any kind of input parameters other than the geometry considered.

Overall, these phonon scattering mechanisms, alone or in combination, can eventually produce a reduction of the thermal conductivity in silicon and its alloys beyond two orders of magnitude with respect to bulk values of the same material.^{36,37} Indeed, in low-dimensional structures, the level of suppression can be so large that other TE properties partially linked to the phonon transport, such as the phonon drag contribution of the Seebeck coefficient, might also be affected.^{38–40} Hence, since nanostructuring also affects thermoelectric properties, it enables a new degree of freedom in the property tuning process, allowing for a further increase in the TE efficiency.

In this Research Update, research advances in silicon and silicon-based thermoelectric nanomaterials—at both the theoretical and experimental level—are presented, with the spotlight on the most recent studies (last decade). Different nanostructures and their fabrication methods are detailed, while the obtained performances and the feasibility of their integration into functional microharvester generators are compared and discussed. Table I lists all the state-of-the-art silicon-based nanostructured materials that are reviewed in this Research Update. Pure silicon-based materials are

shown in a first group where the improvement in TE performance is fully based on size reduction or defect engineering. The second part of Table I groups different nanostructured silicon compounds, such as $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ alloys and a variety of different silicides. In an attempt to order all the data available, this Research Update is sectioned according to the classification depicted in Fig. 2, first covering the research performed on pure silicon and then moving to other silicide compounds in each section. Section II is devoted to nanostructured bulk materials, i.e., macroscopic materials presenting nanoscale features. Subsequently, advances in low-dimensional materials are covered with a special emphasis on thin films and nanowires first and then in more complex systems, such as nanoporosity, superlattices, or core-shell structures. Finally, Sec. VI is devoted to show some successful implementation of nanostructured silicon into functional thermoelectric devices.

II. NANOSTRUCTURED BULK: NANO-POLYCRYSTALS AND DEFECT INDUCED CRYSTALS

One of the most straightforward strategies for reducing the thermal conductivity of silicon without significantly altering the electronic properties—Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity—is the engineering of point, lineal, or extended defects in the lattice. The simplest method is the fabrication of nanometric sized ($\sim 3\text{--}5 \text{ nm}$) polycrystalline silicon. In this regard, the work of Nakamura *et al.*⁴⁵ can be considered the most successful example of this strategy implemented so far. In that work, a strong relationship between the size of the nanograins and the thermal conductivity is found, reaching thermal conductivities lower than 0.8 W/m K for nanograins of 3 nm in diameter. This is indeed remarkable since it probed that κ below the amorphous limit of silicon can be obtained thanks to phonon engineering. As a side-effect, polycrystalline silicon presents a comparatively poorer electronic transport. To avoid this, phonon scattering can be enhanced in single crystal silicon by the addition of impurities to the silicon lattice. In an experimental approach, Stranz *et al.*⁹⁷ studied the effect of different impurity doping—classically used for tuning the electrical properties of silicon—on the thermal conductivity. Up to a 33% reduction of the thermal conductivity takes place when doping silicon to concentrations of $8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is in the order of magnitude at which the optimum power factor is found for silicon. Alternative strategies to engineer lattice defects were also proposed by Bennett *et al.*^{43,44} In these approaches, defects—created by ion implanted silicon atoms—were engineered in the form of vacancies and dislocations. In these cases, the overall crystallinity of the material is preserved, which has the advantage of preserving electronic transport, but these defects strongly suppress phonon transport. This strategy successfully yielded a thermal conductivity reduction down to 6.5 W/m K . A more refined approach on the same ion irradiation idea was conceptualized by Zhu *et al.*⁹⁸ They considered the possibility to use ion beam irradiation to generate a pattern of disordered (amorphous) silicon volumes within the crystalline lattice [Fig. 4(a)]. This would allow us to optimize the size and spacing of such defect volumes. According to these ideas yet to probe experimentally, zT of 0.4 is predicted. Hence, the realization of bulk materials presenting local defect heterogeneity could boost efficiency, presenting an interesting field of research.

TABLE I. Most relevant nanostructured thermoelectric silicon and silicon-alloyed materials experimentally measured and the reported thermoelectric properties at 300 K. NC: nanocrystal, NP: nanoparticle, ϕ : diameter or mean size (if not circular), δ : thickness, \square : cross section (squared), L: length, MBE: molecular-beam epitaxy, P: pitch, SL: superlattice, PC: polycrystalline, MACE: metal-assisted chemical etching, NT: nanotube, SC: single-crystal, VLS: vapor-liquid-solid, TF: thin film, †: old work (before 2015).

Material	Type	Size	N (cm ⁻³)	κ (W/m·K)	σ (S/cm)	S ^{ab} (μ V/K)	zT	References
Silicon	NC bulk	$\phi \sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ NP	2×10^{20}	15	240	-50	0.02	41
† Silicon	Sintered NC bulk	ϕ 100 nm NP	1%	10.5	550	120	0.11	42
Silicon	Dislocated bulk	L 200 nm	4.4×10^{19}	45	180	600	~ 0.045	43
Silicon	Ion-implanted vacancy bulk	...	1.3×10^{19}	6.5	~ 200	-400	0.2	44
Silicon	PC with SL	ϕ 20 nm NC	10^{19}	0.78 ± 0.12	~ 190	~ 220	~ 0.3	45
Silicon	Porous bulk (50%)	ϕ 5 nm	5×10^{19}	1000	...	46
Silicon	Porous TF stripes (44%)	\square $200 \times 6 \mu\text{m}^2$ ϕ 15 nm	3.7×10^{19}	1	55.6	-248	0.1	47
† Silicon	Porous bulk	δ 80 μm	5×10^{19}	7.6	700 ± 200	250 ± 10	0.25 ± 0.05	48
† Silicon	Holey TF	δ 2 μm P 55 nm	5×10^{19}	1.73 ± 0.06	333 ± 20	250 ± 10	0.4 ± 0.05	49
Silicon	Holey TF (aligned)	δ 145 nm	...	7.28	26
Silicon	Holey TF (staggered)	P 30 nm	...	4.36	50
Silicon	Patterned TF	δ 60 nm P 60 nm	...	23	50
Silicon	Holey TF (aligned)	δ 300 nm P 200 nm	2×10^{20}	11	700 ± 50	-107	0.02	51
Silicon	Amorphous TF	δ 90 nm	5×10^{15}	0.8 ± 0.41	52
Silicon	PC TF	δ 108 nm	5×10^{15}	2.4 ± 0.47	52
Silicon	PC TF	δ 100 nm	2×10^{20}	18.5 ± 5.64	53
Silicon	SC TF	\square $660 \times 100 \text{ nm}^2$	2×10^{20}	3.48 ± 1.26	53
Silicon	PC TF	δ 17.5 nm	...	19	54
Silicon	Rough TF	δ 120 nm η 4.2 nm	5×10^{18}	17	165	54
Silicon	Rough TF (nanocoones)	δ 50 nm η 20 nm	...	27 ± 2	55
Silicon	Rough microbeams	\square $1400 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$ \square $120 \times 1000 \text{ nm}^2$	5×10^{18}	41	56
Silicon	Intricated nanobeams	\square $80 \times 75 \text{ nm}^2$...	32	57
Silicon	Porous NW (46%)	ϕ 218 nm ϕ 4.2 nm NP	2.2×10^{20}	2.0 ± 0.1	500 ± 10	200 ± 20	0.31 ± 0.02	17
Silicon	Porous NW (35%–40%)	ϕ 90–150 nm L 30 μm	10^{19}	0.87	58
Silicon	Porous MACE NW array	20–200 nm symmetrical over Si wafer	10^{19}	1.68	131.6	382	0.34	59
† Silicon	Rough SC NW	ϕ 52 nm	7×10^{19}	1.66 ± 0.13	590 ± 20	240 ± 5	0.6	36

TABLE I. (Continued.)

Material	Type	Size	N (cm ⁻³)	κ (W/m·K)	σ (S/cm)	S ^{II} (μ V/K)	zT	References
† Silicon	Super-lattice pattern transferred NW	ϕ 10 nm	2×10^{20}	0.76 ± 0.15	300	~ 120	0.17	37
Silicon	MACE SC NW array	ϕ 250 nm	3×10^{19}	1.8 ± 0.3	~ 200	160	~ 0.15	60
Silicon	MACE SC NW	ϕ 200 nm	2.3×10^{19}	35 ± 2	...	298	...	61
				3.6 ± 0.3	31	699.5	0.13	
Silicon	MACE SC NW (top sintered to bulk)	ϕ 150 nm	5.5×10^{18}	2.95 ± 0.4	29.8	721.5	0.168	62
				2.45 ± 0.3	2.78	714.9	0.186	
				1.75 ± 0.4	2.65	747.8	0.3	
Silicon	Rough SC VLS NW	ϕ 70–120 nm	3×10^{19}	14 ± 2	270	200	0.02	63
Silicon	Rough SC VLS NW	ϕ 50–100 nm	1×10^{19}	17.2 ± 1.4	200 ± 20	330	0.04	64
Silicon	Rough SC VLS NW	ϕ 40 nm	...	17.2 ± 1.4	490 ± 20	225	0.03	65
Silicon	Rough VLC SC NW	ϕ 90.5 nm L 8.9 μ m	$\sim 10^{19}$	6 ± 0.5	66
Silicon	Scalloped SC MACE NW	ϕ 350 nm	...	15 ± 2	67
Silicon	Sintered NP nanobulk (plasma etch)	ϕ 150 nm NP	...	14	510	-125	0.01	68
† Silicon	MACE SC NW	ϕ 100 nm NP	4.6×10^{20}	6.3	1098	-70	0.023	69
† Silicon	Rough VLS SC NW	ϕ 70 nm	...	7.78	56
		η 2.8 nm						
		ϕ 104 nm	5×10^{19}	17	...	190	...	38
		ϕ 122 nm	7×10^{19}	18	...	-190	...	
		ϕ 112 nm	3×10^{19}	2.6	...	440	...	
Silicon	SL ion irradiated NW	ϕ 160 nm	...	~ 2	70
Silicon	SC NT	ϕ 10 nm	...	~ 1	71
Silicon	PCNT fabrics	δ 200 nm NT	10^{20}	0.02	0.8	200	0.08 ± 0.01	72
		δ 200 μ m						
†Si _{0.8} Ge _{0.2}	Sintered NP nanobulk	ϕ 200 nm		2.5	85	125	0.13	73
Si _{0.8} Ge _{0.2}	Sintered NP nanobulk	ϕ 35 nm NP		1.4	20	-140	0.0084	74
Germanium	SC TF	δ 79 nm	2.5×10^{19}	6.1	800	-250	0.24	75
Si _{0.7} Ge _{0.3}	Amorphous TF	δ 137 nm	1.0×10^{20}	1.68 ± 0.7	600	-160	0.27	76
SiGe	PC TF	δ 220 nm	4%	0.53	42.8	77
Si _{0.7} Ge _{0.3}	PC TF	δ 1.5 μ m	1.5×10^{20}	4.0 ± 0.4	520 ± 20	-225	0.15 ± 0.05	78
Si _{0.6} Ge _{0.4}	PC microfilm	δ 15 μ m	2%	1.5	80	-125	0.02	79
SiGe	Holey nanomesh	ϕ 300–20 nm		0.55 ± 0.10		-690	0.035	

TABLE I. (Continued)

Material	Type	Size	N (cm ⁻³)	κ (W/m·K)	σ (S/cm)	S ^a (μV/K)	zT	References
Si _{0.9} Ge _{0.1}	SC VLS NW	ø 75 nm L 5–6 μm ø 65–96 nm	...	1 ± 0.2	80
Si _{0.7} Ge _{0.3}		L 2 μm	...	1.9 ± 0.2	
Si _{0.9} Ge _{0.1}	SC NW	ø 103 nm	...	2.5	81
Si _{0.8} Ge _{0.2}	SC NW	ø 125 nm	1.7 × 10 ¹⁹	3.1 ± 1.5	145	180	0.04	82
† Si _{0.9} Ge _{0.1}	SC VLS NW	ø 160 nm	...	2.5 ± 0.5	83
SiGe	MBE NW	ø ~ 100 nm	...	2.5 ± 0.5	84
Si _{0.8} Ge _{0.2}	SC NW	ø 65 nm	9 × 10 ¹⁹	0.8	850	-110	0.2	85
† Si _{0.9} Ge _{0.1}	SC NW	ø 16 nm	...	2.5	20
SiGe			...					86
Si _{0.7} Ge _{0.3}	Rough SC VLS NW	ø 87 nm L 5 μm η 75 nm	7 × 10 ¹⁸	1.6 ± 0.2	76	180	0.04	87
Si _{0.7} Ge _{0.3}	Rough SC VLS NW	ø 114 nm L 5.5 μm	~10 ¹⁹	4.2 ± 0.3	66
† Ge/Si	Core/shell NW	ø 20 nm	...	2.1 ± 0.4	88
† β-CSi	VLS SC NW	ø 60–100 nm	...	86.5 ± 3.5	225	-1210	0.12	89
† β-CSi	NW (controlled combustion)	ø 90–70 nm	...	6	60	-55	0.001	90
† CrSi ₂	NW	ø 150 nm	...	11 ± 1	1000	150	0.06	91
β-FeSi-SiGe	Nanoincluded NP bulk	ø 100 nm	3%	3.3 ± 0.3	240	-165	0.06 ± 0.03	92
(CrSi ₂) _{0.9}	Nanoincluded NP bulk	ø ~ 2 μm	6.2 × 10 ²⁰	2.1	925	105	0.12	93
(SiGe) _{0.1}	PC bulk	ø ~ 500 nm	...	2.65	445	135	0.1	94
MnSi _{1.74}	Micro-film (bulk)	δ 30–70 μm	8.7 × 10 ¹⁸ 5.3 × 10 ¹⁸	...	108	341	...	95
† Mg ₂ Si			77	302	...	
Mg _{1.98} Li _{0.02} Si			...	7	275	60	0.05	
Mg _{1.98} Li _{0.02}	Bulk		...	1.8	45	140	0.11	96
Si _{0.6} Sn _{0.4}			...					

^aThe Seebeck coefficient sign denotes whether the material is p-type (positive) or n-type (negative).

FIG. 4. Examples of nanobulk approaches. (a) Micrographs showing sub-surface defect-rich regions created in the Si wafers. Dislocation loops promoted on the bulk were created with ion-implantation and subsequent annealing.⁴³ (b) Backscattered SEM image of a nano-inclusion of β -FeSi₂ and SiGe phases.⁹² (c) Schematics showing the synergy of both phases in the enhancement of the thermoelectric properties. The high Seebeck phase (β -FeSi₂) provides the matrix material with a low thermal conductivity induced by microcrystallinity and grain inclusions. The high electrically conductive phase (heavily doped SiGe) percolates the matrix and provides low resistance pathways for charge carriers. Images reproduced/adapted with permission from the authors of Refs. 43 and 92.

Newer and more precise data also yielded the revision of well-established analytical phonon scattering models. Comprehensive theoretical insights were carried out in the works of Kim *et al.*⁹⁹ and Dongre *et al.*¹⁰⁰ where they further tuned the modeling proposed by Wang and Mingo.²⁰ Specifically, more accurate models for point defect scattering—either produced by doping or alloy—and for frequency-dependent boundary scattering—especially concerning polycrystals—are proposed. In these works, authors agreed on the overall reduced suppression effect of these nanograins in low frequency phonons. This refined modeling was also confirmed with *ab initio*-based Monte Carlo simulations.¹⁰¹

Complementary to phonon scattering improvements, some strategies have been considered with the aim of enhancing the power factor of silicon. An interesting approach was proposed by Neophytou *et al.*¹⁰² In this study, they paid attention to the structure at the grain boundary than can be generated if dopant segregation takes place. In these conditions, the depleted grains become potential barriers with large Seebeck coefficients, whereas the grain boundary structure can behave as potential wells with a large electrical conductivity [see Fig. 4(c)]. Yet, experimental evidences on dopant-segregated polycrystalline silicon are still pending to support this promising theoretical strategy.

Aside from strategies based on pure silicon, the alloy of silicon with some other elements, such as Ge, Cr, Mg, Mn, or Fe, provides a relatively low starting thermal conductivity. For instance, bulk SiGe alloys show thermal conductivities of ~ 10 – 5 W/m K,¹⁰³ which allowed for a successful implementation in aerospace applications for decades. The fundamentals of analytical phonon modeling in such alloys were very comprehensively covered by the works of Minnich and Yang,^{15,101} who also considered the effects of nanostructuring. A Rayleigh ω^4 dispersion can accurately model the large suppression of high frequency phonons in these kinds of alloys.

Experimentally, nanostructuring in nanometric size crystals (< 100 nm) of SiGe alloys carried out by Xie and Gupta⁷⁸ was achieved to tailor the thermal conductivity down to ~ 1 W/m K without altering the electronic properties. A similar approach was followed by Stathokostopoulos *et al.*⁹⁵, who sintered Mg₂Si by using the pack cementation method, and by Le Tonquesse *et al.*⁹⁴, who did the same with MnSi_{1.74} and also studied the long-term degradation under operating temperature conditions.

Yet, the state-of-the-art nanostructuring strategies are based on the engineering of nanocomposites of different nano-included phases within the lattice as proposed by Upadhyay⁹³ and Liu.⁹² More specifically, they proposed to embed silicon-germanium nanoclusters (~ 10 wt. %) into CrSi₂ and β -FeSi₂ lattices, respectively. A SEM image of the latter is illustrated in Fig. 4(b). These approaches not only achieved slight thermal conductivity reductions but also increased the charge carrier mobility through the SiGe material while taking advantage of the high Seebeck coefficient shown by the silicide phases. In this way, the composite material benefits from the synergy of the interesting thermoelectric properties of both phases, as schematized in Fig. 4(c).

Overall, bulk nano-defect engineering has achieved remarkable thermoelectric performance improvements. However, the use of such materials into thermoelectric generators still lacks of the same inconvenience as the classical ones do, namely, a complex and laborious assembly of the modules and low flexibility. Moreover, few of those relatively new materials have so far proved long term stability under operation conditions.

III. THIN FILMS

The engineering of thermoelectric materials in a thin film fashion presents several advantages, including an easy implementation

on the silicon-based mainstream microelectronic technology. Additionally, they can be manufactured with relatively simple and standard surface deposition processes, such as conventional Chemical Vapor Deposition (CDV) or evaporation, currently employed in mass-scale production reactors.

The most straightforward approaches are based on the same principles as for the case of bulk materials. Such is the case of polycrystalline thin films proposed by Moradian *et al.*⁵² Here, the out-of-plane phonon scattering enabled us to further reduce thermal conductivity of polysilicon—which features ~ 30 W/m K in the bulk form—to 3.5 W/m K in ~ 100 nm thick films. Similarly, Ferrando-Villalba *et al.*⁵³ tested the differences in thermal conductivity of a single crystal 17.5 nm thick film with those of a polycrystalline counterpart, obtaining values of 19 and 9.7 W/m K, respectively. Both examples show how κ of polycrystalline silicon can still be tailored by including reduced dimensionality to the already present grain boundary scattering. Interestingly, the use of thin films enables us to pattern different surface morphologies, which have deep impact on the phonon transport. This creates further degrees of freedom that research can tune. As an illustrative example, the fabrication of thin-films with highly rough surfaces might result in phonon suppression beyond the Casimir limit, as a high aspect ratio of each individual protrusion effectively acts as phonon traps, suppressing them with multiple surface interactions. In the works of Pennelli *et al.*⁵⁴ and Huang *et al.*,⁵⁵ highly rough thin films were employed. A roughness rms value of 4.2 and 20 nm in films of 120 and 50 nm thick enabled a thermal conductivity reduction of crystalline silicon down to 17 and 27 W/m K, respectively. Both results agree with a clear relationship between the surface roughness and thickness and the achieved κ , with a further reduction as the roughness increased.

Another strategy explored has been the micro/nano-patterning of holes in the thin film, as shown in Figs. 5(c)–5(d). Yanagisawa *et al.*⁵¹ explored the approach in a 300 nm thick film featured within a functional thermoelectric microgenerator, showing that the 200 nm in diameter holes patterned could reduce the thermal conductivity down to 11 W/m K without altering the electronic properties and thus doubling the obtained zT compared to a non-patterned film. Yet, the relatively large size of the holes and the periodic pattern might still allow for straight pathways in certain directions where phonon coherence is not efficiently suppressed.^{26,32} Indeed, the results presented by Tang *et al.*⁴⁹—who instead used a disordered pattern in a 100 nm thick film—show that thermal conductivity can be further reduced to 1.73 W/m K. Hence, the geometry of the perforated membrane (either aligned or staggered) can modify the thermal conductivity by altering the phonon pathway, which is mainly driven by a ballistic transport in such cases. Anufriev *et al.*^{26,32} comprehensively compared the effect of the hole patterning, demonstrating the strong relevance of ballistic transport.

Analogous to bulk materials, alloying has been employed in polycrystalline thin films by different authors. Lu *et al.*⁷⁷ obtained efficient thermoelectric materials, which are straightforwardly implemented in functional microdevices, such as the microgenerator proposed by Koike *et al.*¹⁰⁵ An alternative fabrication technique was suggested by Taniguchi *et al.*,⁷⁵ who reported silicon–germanium films fabricated using molecular beam epitaxy lowering the thermal conductivity to (2 W/m K).

In a further refinement, Ascencio-Hurtado *et al.*⁷⁶ tested the thermal conductivity reduction of PECVD-deposited ~ 200 nm SiGe films with embedded nanocrystals, yielding values as low as 0.53 W/m K and, therefore, demonstrating that the thermal conductivity could be tailored beyond the amorphous limit.

Another original implementation of the thin film technology was developed by Lee and co-workers.^{104,106} In their works, they employed the mainstream 24 nm complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology to embed vertically aligned 80 nm thick Si and Si_{0.97}Ge_{0.03} nanoblades into silicon oxide [see Figs. 5(e) and 5(f)]. Subsequently, a series of metal deposition process patterned the electrical and thermal paths. This approach, mimicking the implementation of vertically aligned transistors, achieved an unprecedentedly high integration level. However, due to the intrinsic monolithic design, thermoelectric properties of the nanoblades themselves have not been reported yet.

IV. NANOWIRES

Perhaps the most recurrent approach for nanostructuring aside of the thin film technology is nanowire engineering. Nanowires (NWs) show excellent potentiality as a pathway for the improvement of thermoelectric transport properties as they present superior exploitation of the size effects compared with thin films, but in contrast to nano-dots still have one free dimension, enabling the fabrication of elongated structures capable of withstanding larger thermal gradients. While there is currently plenty of literature covering silicon nanowires, it is worth highlighting to the reader the relevance of works where authors are able to assess all thermoelectric properties in the same nanowire. Otherwise, while still useful for the community, those results are to be taken carefully, as, for instance, the large error assumed by Houchbaum *et al.*³⁶ and Boukai *et al.*,³⁷ which were never explained theoretically or reproduced experimentally.¹⁶

Horizontal nanowires can be monolithically obtained using a combination of e-beam lithography (EBL), deep reactive ion etching (DRIE), wet etching, and/or directly patterned using focused ion beam (FIB), as sketched in Fig. 6(a). These approaches allow for obtaining monolithic wires, a feature of great interest for the integration of the NWs in microgenerators, since it allows us to reduce the internal device resistance. Examples of recent success cases are the works of Nasr Esfahani *et al.*¹⁰⁷ and Stranz *et al.*¹⁰⁸ who used a combination of patterned masks, DRIE, and wet etching [Fig. 6(b)] to this end. More interestingly, these techniques allow for defining more complex geometries than in classical vertical approaches. As an example, Moradian *et al.*⁵² patterned polysilicon thin films in S-shaped nanowires (Fig. 7), attempting in this way to suppress any ballistic transport. This S-patterning is also interesting in terms of mechanical properties required for their implementation on functional generators, yet no information in this regard was provided. However, they found that the thermal conductivity of such structures did not vary significantly compared to the original film as the cross-plane boundary in combination with the boundary scattering of the nano-grain already suppressed most of the phonons that could be scattered elsewhere. A similar approach was tested by Park *et al.*⁵⁷ in crystalline films. They studied the effect of path tortuosity by introducing cuts of increasing depth in an 80 nm thick strip. In this way,

FIG. 5. Examples of recent silicon thin film implementations. (a) Monocrystalline silicon thin film between two suspended nanocalorimeters, extracted from Ref. 52. (b) SEM image of a silicon nanoribbon, covered by silver nanoparticles after the MACE step.⁵⁴ (c) Sketch of a micropatterned thin film with a staggered pattern in the horizontal direction. Adapted from the work of Tang *et al.*⁴⁹ (d) SEM image of a microfilm patterned with 350 nm pitch holes.⁴⁹ (e) Sketch of a CMOS-based microgenerator device, including vertically aligned p- and n-type silicon nanoblades.¹⁰⁴ (f) Cross section SEM image of the same microdevice.¹⁰⁴

they could reduce the thermal conductivity of the beam from 47 K to 31 W/m K when using a slit depth of 395 nm. These works show how depending on the crystallinity, non-straight NW shapes can be benefited from the ballistic phonon contribution suppression, whereas this effect is minor when the main transport in the NW is already diffusive.

However, the aforementioned techniques are not suitable for large arrays of NWs needed for harvesting applications. The reduced cross section area of just a few NWs unavoidably yields too high electrical resistances for practical thermoelectric generators. Hence, strategies that can implement large arrays of aligned nanowires focus most of the attention. One of the approaches to grow vertically aligned silicon nanowire arrays has been the metal-assisted-chemical-etching (MACE) process [see Fig. 6(a)]. With this technique, n-type highly dense arrays (with filling factors of $\sim 15\%$) of epitaxial and rough nanowires were tested by Elyamny *et al.*^{60,112} Thanks to an optimized deposition of a top electrical collector layer, they could overcome the challenge of the upper side contact, measure the thermoelectrical properties of such arrays, and test the device as an energy harvester. NWs with diameters ranging from 60 to 120 nm showed thermal conductivities of ~ 4.6 W/m K. This

reduced κ is likely related to the high roughness of the NW surfaces produced by MACE and yielded a ready-to-generate material with a competitive power generation capacity of $1 \mu\text{W}/\text{K}^2 \text{cm}^2$. Indeed, the MACE technique has been so fine-tuned that allows for producing half-millimeter NWs, with direct application to macroscopic thermoelectric devices.¹¹³

Vertically aligned nanowires can also be obtained using nonpatterned Deep Reactive Ion Etching (DRIE). As depicted in Figs. 7(b) and 7(c), by alternating cycles of passivation and etching, scalloped nanowires were fabricated by Lee *et al.*⁶⁷ By optimizing the angle and period of the pattern, a significant thermal conductivity reduction could be obtained compared to smooth nanowires. In these cases, even considering a fully specular phonon boundary scattering, the angle of the pattern allows us to redirect the backward part of the incident phonon flux. For nanowires of 190 nm diameter, κ was reduced from ~ 35 down to ~ 15 W/K m using a scallop period of 55 nm. Finally, analogously to those NWs fabricated by MACE, this strategy has the advantage of preserving the electronic properties of the original substrate.

Alternatively, arrays of epitaxially aligned nanowires can also be fabricated using bottom-up approaches. The most common is

FIG. 6. (a) Schematics illustrating the main nanowire fabrication pathways. (b)–(d) SEM examples of nanowires fabricated with each of the described approaches. From left to right: top-down lithography and RIE (b),¹⁰⁸ top-down MACE (c),¹⁰⁹ and bottom-up VLS (d).¹¹⁰ (e) and (f) SEM examples of NW prepared for their integration in devices. (e) Metal deposition used as a top current collector of MACE NW arrays employed by Dimaggio and Pennelli.¹¹¹ (f) Double-side epitaxially integrated VLS-grown nanowires used by Gadea Díez *et al.*⁶³

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the Vapor–Liquid–Solid (VLS) method, carried out inside a Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) reactor [see Fig. 6(c)]. Using this approach, Lee *et al.*⁶⁵ produced dispersed arrays of nanowires using gold colloids as catalyst and successfully transferred to test platforms of individual nanowires of sizes down to 22 nm, measuring κ of values as low as ~ 7 W/m K. The VLS approach has the advantage of being especially suitable for the integration of the NWs into functional devices, allowing them to grow even in the horizontal direction. In their works, Gadea Díez *et al.* and Sojo Gordillo *et al.*^{63,66} explored the thermoelectric properties of both individual and NW arrays of integrated p-doped rough nanowires (rms roughness

> 50 nm) with diameters in the range of 50–100 nm. They demonstrated that a double-side epitaxial attachment is possible using this method, enabling the use of this approach in high-performance micro-thermoelectric generators.

However, the effect of phonon suppression has an impact on the Seebeck coefficient too as the phonon drag contribution is also severely tailored. By tuning the doping level of the nanowires, Sadhu *et al.*³⁸—supported by their results on silicon nanowires of ~ 100 nm diameter—reported significant lower values of the Seebeck coefficient in those nanowires than the coefficient of bulk silicon with the same doping concentration. Therefore, a shift on the optimal doping

FIG. 7. Some images of complex shapes. (a) S-shaped nanowires from the work of Moradian *et al.*⁵² (b) and (c) Scalloped nanowires of Lee *et al.*⁶⁷

FIG. 8. Seebeck coefficient and power factor dependence with the doping level and the nanostructuring. Gray filled squares represent silicon bulk values, and the gray solid line represents the fitting of such data.^{16,97,114,115} Black solid circles stand for monolithic silicon nanowires. The black solid line is the fit of all data.^{38,63,64,112} Open circles represent highly porous (>50%) silicon nanowires. The dotted line is the fitting.^{17,59}

level of silicon nanowires with respect to bulk takes place.⁶⁴ The effect of nanostructuring on the silicon Seebeck coefficient reported by the cited sources is summarized in Fig. 8.

Additionally, Gadea and Sojo also showed significant thermal conductivity reductions (~ 15 W/m K) compared to values expected to smooth silicon nanowires, attributed to a very high level of roughness. These results are in agreement with the discussion of Maurer *et al.*¹¹⁶ and Yang *et al.*¹³ who both reported theoretical and experimental direct relationships between this super-Casimirian scattering rate observed and the surface-to-volume ratio (SVR) of the nanowires, respectively. Indeed, earlier experiments on individual nanowires already showed the high dependency of the thermal conductivity with the roughness, as studied in detail by Lim *et al.*⁵⁶ Similar results were reported by Lee *et al.*⁶¹ who found conductivities of 34.7 W/m K for thicker VLS-grown nanowires (200 nm diameter) and smoother surfaces (7 nm of rms roughness), confirming the observed trend with the SVR. Indeed, the effect of the SVR can be strongly related to the κ reduction and can be extended to all kinds of nanostructures, as illustrated in Fig. 9.

In addition to the boundary defect scattering inherent of nanowires, phonon transport can be further tailored in these structures by the implementation of complementary scattering mechanisms, such as impurities, defects, or alloys analogously to the approach described in bulk materials. Alloy phonon scattering mechanism strongly depends on the difference of masses between the elements composing the alloy. While alloying with any element can serve this purpose, different isotopes, such as ^{28}Si and ^{30}Si , are ideal candidates as they share the very same electronic/chemical properties except for the mass. This approach was conceptualized in the work of Rojo and Rurali.¹²² In their work, they carried out atomistic molecular dynamics to characterize the dependence of the thermal conductivity with the relative isotope concentration. A reduction of up to 20% was predicted using this approach. Almost

simultaneously, Mukherjee *et al.*¹²³ obtained the first reported isotope blended CVD-growth nanowires. Using Raman thermometry, they compared the peak shift of natural silicon wires with those isotopically engineered, showing a reduction of 30%. In a similar approach, Ci *et al.*¹²⁴ identified an enhancement of the thermal conductivity of almost 10% in nanowires isotopically enriched to the 99.92% of ^{28}Si , as opposed to naturally occurring Si, where traces of ^{29}Si and ^{30}Si are also found. Both studies are very illustrative examples of how the level of mass mismatch on the lattice hinders phonon transport accordingly.

Isotopic engineered mixes are highly interesting from an academic point of view, but the price of pure isotope precursor species

FIG. 9. Thermal conductivity of silicon nanostructures with different geometries of the literature^{22,64,117–121} as a function of surface-area-to-volume ratio (SVR). The data are modeled considering the phonon-boundary scattering proposed by Ref. 13. Figure inspired from the work of Ref. 17.

($^{28}\text{SiH}_4$ and $^{30}\text{SiH}_4$) required for the fabrication of such nanowires makes them less attractive than blending silicon with other elements of group IV. Germanium is by far the most used element as the performance of bulk and thin film SiGe alloys is well known, and the VLS approach is straightforwardly implemented using a widely available germane (GeH_4) precursor. The thermal performance in the shape of nanowires was studied from a theoretical point of view by Chen *et al.*¹²⁵ and experimentally Yin *et al.*⁸⁰ In their works, they predicted thermal conductivities five times lower than bulk values measured by Dismukes *et al.*¹⁰³ These predictions were accompanied by the experimental studies of Kim *et al.*,⁸³ Lee *et al.*,⁸⁵ Martinez *et al.*,⁸² El Sachat *et al.*,⁸⁴ and Sojo Gordillo *et al.*^{66,87} In these works, the low thermal conductivity predicted was confirmed, with measured values as low as 1.5 W/m K. Interestingly, the thermal conductivity observed in these alloyed NWs with such a strong suppression of high frequency phonons is driven by large wavelength ones. This yields the observation of ballistic effects at room temperature reported by Hsiao *et al.*, with a clear dependency of κ on the NW length when this dimension is below the mean free path (8 μm).⁸⁶ This discovery remarks the relevance of these effects when engineering microthermoelectric generators using this material as a local minimum of NW thermal conductance might be achieved with relatively short—and therefore compact—NW lengths. Finally, it is worth highlighting the works of Martinez *et al.* and Sojo Gordillo *et al.*, who were able to fully characterize heavily p-doped nanowires, yielding zT values two times larger than the bulk alloy. Remarkably, the latter study also demonstrates the feasibility of epitaxial integration of these kinds of nanowires into silicon-based thermoelectric generators, a key feature when using bottom-up approaches that guaranties low internal resistances within the generator.

An alternative alloy candidate considered is β -SiC. Theoretical works, such as those of Termentzidis *et al.*,¹²⁶ have predicted relatively low thermal conductivities for nanowires, ~ 5 compared to the measured 300 W/m K expected for the bulk form at room temperature. These results were corroborated experimentally by Valentín *et al.*,⁹⁰ who measured ~ 6 W/m K in 70 nm diameter unintentionally heavily n-type doped nanowires fabricated by the controlled combustion of Si with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) microparticles. They also assessed the electronic properties with electrical conductivities of 60 S/m but relatively low Seebeck coefficients of -55 $\mu\text{V/K}$. However, these results did not agree with the prior measurements of Lee *et al.*,⁸⁹ who reported a very high figure of merit at room temperature of 0.12, boosted by a really high Seebeck coefficient of -1.21 mV/K. These large S values could be caused by a relatively lower number of impurities and a more defect-free growth achieved with the VLS-CVD process used, which could explain at least partially the larger thermal conductivities found (86.5 \pm 3.5 W/m K for 60–100 nm diameter nanowires) and also relatively high electrical conductivities measured of 225 S/cm. Overall, more research is required on this interesting material, which has shown to have exceptional mechanical properties, thermal and chemical stability. These characteristics make this material ideal for their implementation in very harsh environments. Finally, metal silicide nanowires have recently been successfully synthesized, such as the case of the β -FeSi₂ NWs reported by some authors^{127,128} or the CoSi ones.¹²⁹ However, these promising efficient compounds have not been yet thermoelectrically characterized with the exception of the CrSi₂ NWs reported by Zhou *et al.*⁹¹

V. COMPLEX HETEROSTRUCTURES

Among all the nanostructuring options, nanowires are clearly getting a large fraction of research efforts in the last few decades thanks to the aforementioned implementation advantages with respect to other structures. However, in recent years, complementary strategies relying on material heterogeneity have been implemented in diverse forms with the aim of further reducing the thermal conductivity and/or improving the power factor. These strategies have the additional benefit of adding one or more tunable parameter that can help targeting the phonons frequencies not fully suppressed by the conventional nanostructuring strategy used.

A. Nanoporosity

Nanoporosity is the simplest of the material heterogeneity approaches. A material with pores below 10 nm has both the phonon and electronic band structure altered in a similar way, as sketched in Fig. 1 for NWs with diameters below this diameter. In principle, the increased scattering of phonons has a positive impact on the TE performance. However, electron scattering is also raised and might hinder an improvement in the overall σ/κ ratio. Nevertheless, in the particular case of silicon, the electronic DOS modification can also boost the Seebeck coefficient, yielding an overall enhancement of zT . In this regard, a comprehensive analytical modeling of such structures was proposed by Lee *et al.*¹²

A successful fabrication approach of porous silicon was accomplished via chemical etching (and surfactant) by de Boor *et al.*⁴⁸ In their work, they studied the tailoring of κ from bulk silicon down to 7.6 W/m K with a porosity of 60%. The effect of porosity on the Seebeck coefficient was studied by Valalaki *et al.*⁴⁶ They obtained highly porous crystalline silicon using electrochemical etching. Remarkably, they found that a maximum of roughly 1 mV/K can be achieved for films presenting a porosity of around 50%. This represented a fivefold increase compared to the original material with a doping level of 3×10^{19} cm^{-3} . This idea was applied to thin films, as showed by Ziouche *et al.*⁴⁷ They tailored the thermal conductivity of a heavily n-type doped polysilicon thin film of 1 μm from 31 to ~ 1 W/m K with a porosity of around 44%. However, the relatively bigger porous sizes—ranging in the 10–50 nm range—did not have such a large impact on the electrical properties. In that case, the electrical conductivity was tailored by 25%, while the Seebeck coefficient was reduced by 3%. Hence, in that case, the remarkable zT of 0.1 at room temperature could be mostly attributed to the high phonon suppression achieved.

Parallely, Zhang *et al.*⁵⁹ and Ferrando-Villalba *et al.*⁵⁸ implemented this approach on silicon nanowires. In their work, individual porous Si nanowires prepared by MACE (see Fig. 10) showed thermal conductivities as low as 1.68 and 0.87 W/m K, respectively, for 80–100 nm diameter wires with 35%–40% porosity. Pores ranging from 5 to 30 nm were obtained using this approach. Interestingly, Zhang related the pore size distribution to the measured TE properties, finding an optimal point with sizes around ~ 12 nm, which yielded a remarkable zT value of 0.085 at room temperature. Other studies using the MACE fabrication pathway were reported by Kashiwagi *et al.*⁶² and Sadhu *et al.*³⁸ In their works, they tailored the thermal conductivity below 3 and 2.6 W/m K, respectively, while keeping the electrical conductivity at 30 S/cm (roughly 30% of the

FIG. 10. (a) Schematic illustration for the formation mechanism of porous Si by using the metal assisted chemical etching method. (b) SEM cross-sectional view of porous Si with a porosity of ~60% obtained by Ziouche *et al.*⁴⁷ Porous cavities of ~15 nm are observed. TEM (c) and HRTEM (d) of porous Si nanowires studied by Zhang *et al.*⁵⁹

original bulk substrate value) in the first case. Interestingly, analogous to the work of Ziouche *et al.*⁴⁷ for thin films, they observed a drastic increase in the Seebeck coefficient compared to bulk that ultimately yielded impressive $zT = 0.3$ at room temperature in the case of Kashiwagi. Yet, the most comprehensive study using this approach has been carried out by Yang *et al.*¹⁷ They confirmed high RT zT of Ziouche and Kashiwagi for nanowires of ~150 nm diameter, doping levels of $2.2 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and porosities of ~46%. Additionally, they successfully used the theoretical modeling of boundary scattering provoked by the nanopore voids proposed by Yang *et al.*¹²¹ in order to fit their data. In this approach, the surface to volume ratio SVR is considered directly proportional to the scattering rate in an analogous way as it was used for the boundary scattering modeling of very rough nanowires.¹³ Indeed, their data included in Fig. 9 properly matched the trend.

Hence, one of the most relevant conclusions derived of all aforementioned works on nanoporous nanowires is that, as was concluded for monocrystalline nanowires, the large modification of the Seebeck coefficient induced by nanoporosity shifts the optimal doping value. However, in this case, the effect showed to be positive for the Seebeck coefficient. Hence, at the light of the reported doping level used for the aforementioned studies, it is likely that doping levels of $>10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ are optimal in these cases, as depicted in Fig. 8. Additionally, further studies are required on the stability of these structures, especially under the conditions expected for thermoelectric generation, i.e., moderate temperatures (300–500 K) and flowing currents (1–500 pA/nm²). So far, no long-term studies have been carried out in this regard.

Another radically different approach that benefits from a high porosity is the use of silicon-based nanotubes. The first reported structure consisting of very thin walls (~10 nm) was fabricated by Wingert *et al.*⁷¹ Using nanocalorimeters, they could measure the mechanical stiffness and very low thermal conductivities of ~1 W/m K for such structures, composed of just silicon. Later on, Morata *et al.*⁷² conceived self-supported mesoporous fabric-like structures composed of nanotubes with a double shell of silicon oxide coated by a second layer of heavily doped polysilicon. This constitutes a

great advance in what regards the scalability of the manufacturing method for the fabrication of large-area and cost-effective thermoelectric materials. Using this structure, they obtained a material that could sustain large cross-plane thermal gradients and whose power generation per weight unit (1.1 mW/g K²) is so far unbeatable.

B. Superlattices

Superlattices consist in the intercalation of different materials with a certain periodicity. In this way, the boundaries between materials partially reflect incident phonons, largely hindering their transport. However, ballistic effects need to be considered in their design order to effectively suppress a larger number of phonon frequency modes, as described in the Introduction.

The implementation of superlattices on the axial direction of the nanowires was considered theoretically by Zhang *et al.*²⁸ They predicted using Non-Equilibrium Molecular Dynamics (NEMD) simulation the influence of the periodic length of a heterostructured Si/Ge beam. Remarkably, they compared the differences between a nanowire with an evenly spaced phase and the one whose phases followed an increased period. For phase periods shorter than 5 nm, the evenly spaced model showed increasing thermal conductivities, whereas in the non-evenly spaced counterpart, κ decreased further. This results further evidenced the relevance of coherent—i.e., ballistic—transport and how this can be hindered by simply engineering non-periodic superlattices and/or phase periods larger than the mean free path.

Experimentally, one of the simplest approaches was carried out by Zhao *et al.*⁷⁰ They tested this concept over monocrystalline Si NWs that were locally irradiated with He ions with energies of 30–36 keV. This ended up with a periodic pattern of pristine unirradiated sections intercalated with the amorphous irradiated ones. In this way, they achieved a stable value of the thermal conductivity (~2 W/m K) for doses higher than $\sim 8 \times 10^{16} \text{ at./cm}^2$. This κ is close to the characteristic value of amorphous silicon, suggesting that the amorphous phases effectively destroyed any phonon coherency despite the presence of monocrystalline sections.

The use of different alloy compositions was exploited by Ferrando-Villalba *et al.*¹³⁰ using vertically stacked—or superlattices—compositional gradients of $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$, as illustrated in Figs. 11(a) and 11(b). Here, with a lattice period of 26 nm, the thermal conductivity was tailored to ~ 2.2 W/m K. In a continuation work,²⁹ they studied—using lattice dynamics calculations—why these obtained thermal conductivities were higher or lower than those obtained for the $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ thin films of the same thickness depending on the period of the superlattice used. They concluded that the simultaneous effects of mass scattering, graded interface scattering, and coherent interference from the lattice periodicity drive the phonon transport in these kinds of structures.

However, the fabrication of such sharp interfaces in NW remains very challenging. In this regard, Ben Amor *et al.*¹³¹ tested an approach based on the engineering of pure Si and pure Ge allotrope heterostructured nanowires on the thermal conductivity [see Figs. 11(c) and 11(d)]. The fabrication of those NWs consisted in using plastic deformation by applying a radial compressive stress. Yet, approaches based on obtaining compositionally sharp interfaces, such as the report of Periwal *et al.*¹³³ using fast changes in the gas flows during the VLS growth of NWs, yielded transition interfaces of few tens of nanometers [Figs. 11(e) and 11(f)]. This is caused by the “mass inertia” of the eutectic and requires a dynamic temperature control of the process in order to be tailored. Hence,

FIG. 11. (a) Schematic of a compositionally graded superlattice thin film studied by Ferrando-Villalba *et al.*¹³⁰ (b) SEM (left) and TEM (right) of a cross section of the described superlattice. (c) Schematics of an array of nanowires radially compressed and transformed to the 2H phase proposed by Ben Amor *et al.*¹³¹ (d) HRTEM image of one of these nanowires. The right insets represent the FFT of both phases. Extracted from Vincent *et al.*¹³² (e) TEM image of a compositional Si/SiGe heterostructure NW obtained by Periwal *et al.*¹³³ (f) Chart showing the Ge composition inertia of the Si/SiGe interfaces studied with EELS by Periwal *et al.*¹³³

FIG. 12. (a) Schematics of a quantum well produced by the energy band mismatch in a core(Ge)-shell(Si) thin nanowire structure.¹³⁴ (b) HRTEM of the SiGe/Ge core-shell structure fabricated and characterized by Park *et al.*¹³⁵ (c)–(e) HRTEM and EDX analysis, showing the radial compositional distribution achieved by David *et al.*¹³⁶

FIG. 13. Several examples of μ TEG prototypes. (a) and (b) Planar unileg microgenerator using SiGe thin films fabricated by Koike *et al.*¹⁰⁵ (c)–(h) Similar planar unileg approach using unileg holed silicon.⁵¹ (i)–(k) CMOS approach using buried silicon nanoblades and buried metallic heat exchangers.¹⁰⁴ (l) High power density CMOS generator based on the lateral bulk flow designed by Tomita *et al.*¹⁴² (m) and (n) Unileg generator based on suspended micro-platforms used by Sojo Gordillo *et al.* to integrate arrays of VLS-grown silicon nanowires horizontally.⁶⁴

there is little experimental evidences of these promising approaches implemented in nanowires.

C. Core-shell

An alternative strategy that allows for further phonon suppression is the use of core-shell structures. They consist of nanowires with radial heterostructure, typically featuring a combination of Si, Ge, or SiGe core/shell structures. In this way, the interface between the two layers localizes the phonons and provides a mechanism to reduce the thermal conductivity. Indeed, global κ of the

core-shell structure can be lowered below κ of the individual layers if they were used separately. Additionally, for very thin structures (<20 nm in diameter), the mismatch in the energy bands of both layers can generate a potential well even in intrinsic nanowires [Fig. 12(a)]¹³⁴ in a similar way as the grain dopant segregation discussed by Neophytou *et al.*¹⁰² for the nanocrystalline bulk. However, this interesting approach has not been explored for thermoelectric purposes yet.

Non-equilibrium molecular dynamics has been extensively used to simulate the thermal properties of these structures.¹³⁷ One of the most interesting results is the non-monotonic shell thickness

dependent thermal conductivity of core(Ge)-shell(Si) nanowires found by Chen *et al.*¹³⁸ They calculated that in thin nanowires (10–20 nm) when increasing the shell thickness, the thermal conductivity of the whole NW decreases first, but it eventually reaches a turning point and then begins to increase upon further coating thickness. This phenomenon is explained with the two competing effects of increasing the silicon layer. Increasing the shell increases the cross-sectional area and thus decreases the phonon boundary scattering, yielding larger thermal conductivities. However, the interface created between both layers generates a phonon resonance effect, which localizes the phonons and reduces thermal conductivity.

Experimentally, a first approach to this concept was proposed by Pan *et al.*¹³⁹ They tuned the phonon scattering by an electron-beam deposition of a scattered layer of Ge crystals over the surface of vertically aligned 100 nm diameter silicon nanowires, which reduced the thermal conductivity to 45% (from 9 to 5 W/m K). Yet, nanowires with core shell structures as such were synthesized by Wingert *et al.*⁸⁸ and Patriarche *et al.*¹⁴⁰ The first reported an attempt to measure the thermal properties of such nanostructures (15–20 nm in diameter) using suspended microcalorimeters, finding only slightly differences between the core-shell and pure Ge nanowires. However, the fabrication process itself is not without its challenges. The residual strain between the Si shell and the Ge core [see Figs. 12(c)–12(e)] was investigated and subsequently tailored by David *et al.*¹³⁶ by using a fast thermal annealing process. In addition, Han *et al.*¹⁴¹ also reported doping segregation in the core of these structures by analyzing with Atom Probe Tomography (ATP) nanowires grown at different temperatures. Finally, a comprehensive thermal characterization was reported by Park *et al.*¹³⁵ They were able to assess the thermal conductivity of smooth 42 nm diameter nanowires [Fig. 12(b)], showing a Ge core and an ~3 nm SiGe shell. While reduced κ values of 11 W/m K were observed, those do not represent a further reduction of the conductivity with respect to homogeneous SiGe NWs. This was likely due to the rather thin Ge shell, comparable to the already native oxide shell present in the homogeneous nanowires. Therefore, while this approach has yet to show its potential, the possibility of tuning both thermal and electrical properties is of great interest from a thermoelectric point of view.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION IN FUNCTIONAL DEVICES

Although the focus of this Research Update is not on thermoelectric devices, it is worth highlighting some successful implementation of the nanomaterials described in this Research Update in fully functional devices. In this regard, the great interest in the use of silicon as thermoelectric material is mainly due to the intrinsic compatibility with mainstream microfabrication techniques. Not surprisingly, as in Fig. 13, the majority of applications that have raised recently are based on the Micro-Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) technology. Additionally, these technologies are ideal for the implementation of low-dimensional materials since their integration is simpler.

Concerning micro-harvesters, silicon-based devices have reached in recent years the $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ range, considered the threshold for their application as power sources for the Internet of Things

(IoT).⁶ One of the simplest approaches is based on self-supported nanostructured materials, such as the already mentioned case of silicon nanotube fabrics of Morata *et al.*⁷² or the MACE vertical arrays of NWs obtained by Pennelli and co-workers.⁶⁰ In those materials, only a good external electrical contact must be guaranteed. Yet, many other strategies vary from the use of thin films in lateral architectures. Alternating crystalline silicon films with p- and n-type doping were used in suspended films by Ferrando-Villalba *et al.*¹⁴³ More complex materials were also used in this planar configuration, with SiGe or holey poly-silicon [see Figs. 13(a)–13(h)] proposed by Koike *et al.*¹⁰⁵ and Yanagisawa *et al.*⁵¹ Moreover, the replication of the classical TEGs based on π -modules using the nanometric CMOS technology was proposed by Lee and co-workers; see Figs. 5(e) and 5(f)^{104,106} and the work of Tomita *et al.* [Figs. 13(r) and 13(s)].¹⁴² In all these cases, the device zT is not the major concern as most TE-powered deployed IoT sensor nodes would simply require a minimum power input regardless of the efficiency of the generator as the TEG is just scavenging a fraction of useful energy from a waste source that would be ejected anyway. Yet, improved thermal management as the lateral unileg architecture based on a micro-suspended platform developed by Fonseca and co-workers has proven to enhance the power output with a simple approach.^{64,144–146}

VII. CONCLUSIONS: PROSPECTS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

Along this article, Update, the most promising approaches to develop nanostructured silicon-based compounds as thermoelectrically active materials have been reviewed. This Research Update covered from bulk nanostructuring to the use of gradually more complex low-dimensional materials that take advantage of different phonon scattering mechanisms and eventually modifications in the electronic band structure for the enhancement of the thermoelectric figure of merit.

According to the existing literature, significant improvements in zT have been achieved over bulk silicon by defect engineering, mainly boosted by the enormous phonon transport reduction observed in such defective materials. Nanograined silicon and defect-rich lattices fabricated by ion implantation are the most effective strategies reported so far. Complementarily, interesting results are archived in multiphase materials, for which segregated phases can be selected to modulate Seebeck effect and thermal transport or electronic conduction. However, these improvements on the intrinsic zT do not solve all the practical limitations that conventional TE materials face when are integrated into functional micro-generators.

In this regard, finite sized structures, such as thin films or nanowires, enable easier implementations on functional micro-devices because of the intrinsic compatibility with the mainstream MEMS fabrication technologies. With the advances in thin film deposition techniques, this approach represents a very cost-effective and scalable way of reducing the thermal conductivity while keeping a straightforward integration route. Therefore, it is not surprising that most of the successful implementation of nanostructured silicon in functional devices are currently based on the thin film technology, while the field is gradually integrating a wider

variety of 1D structures as their fabrication technologies become more standardized. 1D structures (nanowires) present further advantages in what regards thermoelectric efficiency enhancement thanks to their superior exploitation of size effect and an elongated structure ideal for the withstanding of thermal gradients. However, although there are a large number of highly comprehensive studies in the field, the integration of these structures into devices—similarly to the final applications—is still scarce. Other nanostructures, such as heterostructures, core-shell, or superlattices, are still quite immature, existing few reports on their complete TE characterization. Yet, results obtained so far are very promising and exciting, suggesting that these types of complex nanostructures could foster future research in this area.

All in all, in the last two decades, silicon has reborn as a feasible thermoelectric material. This renewed interest is boosted by the increasing maturity of micro- and nano-fabrication technologies and the promising performance enhancement reported for nanostructured silicon and silicon-based materials. Thanks to that, pioneering examples of thermoelectric generators are being developed, demonstrating the relevance of nanostructured silicon for the generation of future energy harvesting devices with the application in exciting fields, such as the Internet of Things.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This investigation was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Education through an FPU grant (Grant No. FPU18/01494) and the Generalitat de Catalunya-AGAUR (Grant No. 2017 SGR 1421), 50% co-financed by the European Union Regional Development Fund (ERDF) within the framework of the ERDF Operational Program of Catalonia 2014–2020, and supported by the University and Research Secretary of the Business and Knowledge Department of the Generalitat de Catalonia in the project FEM-IoT (Grant No. 001-P-001662). This research was also supported by the Spanish National Research Agency (AEI) through Project No. PID2019-110142RB-C21 (AEI/FEDER, EU) “THERMOLOGICS.”

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Jose Manuel Sojo Gordillo: Writing – original draft (equal). **Alex Morata:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead). **Carolina Duque Sierra:** Writing – original draft (supporting). **Marc Salleras:** Writing – review & editing (equal). **Luis Fonseca:** Writing – review & editing (equal). **Albert Tarancón:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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